

IRISCC

D7.2

Strategic IRISCC Access Programme - Version 2.0

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Abstract

Key words

Access programme, transnational, virtual, calls for access, cross-disciplinarity, fast-track access

This document presents Version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme and its updated access roadmap. Building on lessons learned from the first two Transnational Access (TA) calls in 2025, Version 2 introduces strategic refinements to strengthen scientific integration, multi-RI engagement, and more comprehensive climate change risk (CCR) approaches, while maintaining the programme's core objectives and open, bottom-up character. In parallel, Virtual Access (VA) provides access to existing RIs digital services while improving the access mechanisms and functionalities since the first release of the Catalogue of Services (CoS) in April 2025, with ongoing efforts to improve visibility, monitoring, and user feedback. The updated roadmap confirms the planned TA-VA call schedule, with upcoming calls (including Call 3 launched in February 2026) implementing selected measures, notably refined disciplinarity assessment, stronger CCR integration, reinforced multi-RI use, and increased TA-VA linkages. The results are expected to improve the quality of the user proposals, enhanced uptake across a more diverse user community, and strengthened scientific and societal impact. An annex provides access statistics from Calls 1 and 2 and initial VA usage indicators.

Revision History

Version	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
v1.0	25/02/2025	Submitted v1.0	Sabine Philippin (CNRS)
v1.1	03/03/2026	First Draft of v2.0	Sabine Philippin (CNRS)
V1.2	26/05/2026	Second Draft of v2.0	Sabine Philippin (CNRS)
V1.3	18/06/2026	Second Draft of v2.0 Revision	Janne Rinne (LUKE) Ulf Mallast (UFZ)
V2.0	30/06/2026	Submitted v2.0	Sabine Philippin (CNRS)

Document Description			
Strategic IRISCC Access programme and updates (M18, 26, 34, 36) (version 2.0)			
Work Package Number 7			
Document Type	R - Document, report		
Document Status	Under EC Review	Version	v2.0
Dissemination Level	Public		
Copyright Status	<p>This material by Parties of the IRISCC Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>		
Lead partner	CNRS https://www.iriscc.eu/publication/strategic-access-programme		
Document Link	https://www.iriscc.eu/publication/strategic-access-programme		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.21065850		
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Estimated Delivery date	May 2026 (M26)		
Actual Delivery date	30/06/2026 (M27)		

Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
CCR	Climate change-related risks
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, is an internationally coordinated multi-model climate simulation framework supporting assessments of the IPCC of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP).
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment, provides higher-resolution regional climate projections derived from CMIP simulations for impact and adaptation studies.
CoS	Catalogue of Services
ECA&D	European Climate Assessment & Dataset, is a European collaboration that collects and harmonises in situ climate observations to produce quality-controlled datasets and gridded products for climate monitoring and impact studies
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
RI, RIs	Research Infrastructure, Research Infrastructures
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
TA	Transnational Access
T&S	Travel and subsistence
VA	Virtual Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme

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Executive summary

Version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme builds on the strategic direction established in Version 1 (Deliverable D7.2 Strategic IRISCC Access programme and updates (M18, 26, 34, 36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102251>) and reflects a focused refinement rather than a major redesign. Its purpose is to consolidate conditions for high-quality, cross-domain research that supports climate change-related risk (CCR) assessment and adaptation, while preserving the programme's core objectives and an open, bottom-up call approach.

Key lessons from first two IRISCC Transnational Access (TA) Calls (2025): User demand increased substantially between Calls 1 and 2, with eligible proposals rising from 26 to 57 and a broader geographic reach, including a notable share of users from outside Europe. The user community remains predominantly academic, while participation from public authorities and SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises) is emerging. Scientific domains are diversifying. While atmospheric sciences remain prominent, biosphere and hydrosphere domains are strongly represented, and new technical and applied fields appear (bio-medical sciences, chemistry, material sciences, etc.). Requests for facilities/installations expanded from 15 to 25, indicating broader exploration of the IRISCC landscape and a less concentrated demand across a few single research infrastructure (RI) domains. Physical access remains the dominant mode, with continued interest in hybrid access and limited demand for purely remote access.

At the same time, analysis and reviewer feedback indicate challenges in the quality and effective integration. While many project self-identify as inter-, multi-, or transdisciplinary, the cross-disciplinary approach is not always reflected in robust methodological integration or a coherently designed work plan. Truly integrative approaches remain limited, highlighting the existing barriers for effectively bringing together different disciplines within a single user project and for engaging non-academic stakeholders. Concerning CCR determinants, nearly half of the projects still focus on single determinants. Although partially integrated efforts are observed, genuinely integrated approaches (e.g., in terms of user group composition, project design, impact assessment) remain limited. The same applies to fully integrated hazard-exposure-vulnerability approaches, indicating a need for clearer guidance and incentives for more holistic CCR designs and preparation time.

Progress and challenges in virtual access (VA): VA services are described in detail in the Catalogue of Services (CoS) and have been accessible since March 2025, building on established RI services which are continuously available through a unique VA portal without application requirements. The VA portfolio includes services from a broad range of scientific domains supporting climate risk analysis, data access, visualisation and analytical environments. Initial indicators show international visibility and uptake, though variability across services reflects differences in RI maturity, target communities and service types. Initial indicators show international visibility and uptake, though variability across services reflects differences in target communities and service types. As many services are long-

standing RI offerings, accessible through RI-specific portals, current monitoring mainly captures overall service usage rather than IRISCC-specific attribution. Harmonised management, monitoring and feedback tools are being improved for laying the groundwork for expanding access to integrated, user-oriented climate risk information across Europe.

Strategic refinements in Version 2: In response to these lessons learnt, Version 2 proposes a set of targeted measures to be implemented progressively across the calls. Priorities include: (i) strengthening evaluation of cross-disciplinary integration using clearer indicators; (ii) encouraging multi-RI engagement to reduce thematic silos; (iii) providing more time and support for early-stage co-design and user group composition; (iv) promoting more integrated CCR approaches in call texts (including success stories) and in the evaluation process; (v) strengthening TA-VA linkages by encouraging TA with VA-supported services; (vi) increasing visibility and uptake of underutilised installations; (vii) exploring thematic or problem-focused calls for high-impact climate risk challenges; and (viii) strengthening integration of societal dimensions and vulnerability in CCR research. Particular attention is given to optimising user financial support to enhance participation and facilitate more integrated and cross-disciplinary collaboration. These measures are supported through reinforced communication and training for both users and providers.

Roadmap and focus of Calls 3-4 focus: The updated roadmap maintains the overall call schedule, while further reinforcing VA as a continuously available opportunity embedded in the overall access strategy. Call 3 (February-April 2026) implemented selected refinements: a clearer disciplinary assessment (including an explicit mono-disciplinary option), stronger encouragement of integrated CCR determinants, reinforced multi-RI engagement supported by communication and training. It also introduced an evaluation element in the TA proposal assessment process to encourage the effective integration of VA services into project design. Call 4 (launched in July 2026) will build on the same updated framework, while allowing rapid refinement of communication and access strategies based on the outcomes from Call 3. Additional measures (e.g., extended call timelines, targeted topical calls, stronger focus on underutilised facilities, societal-dimension prioritisation) will be further explored for subsequent calls.

Expected impact: The proposed refinements are expected to progressively improve proposal quality, strengthen cross-domain climate risk assessment capability, increase reuse and visibility of outputs, and enhance relevance for adaptation planning and climate risk management. Overall, the IRISCC Access Programme remains on track and is consolidating its initial approach, while progressively strengthening integration, widening the diversity of user communities, and enhancing scientific and societal impact.

Revision of the programme: The access strategy will be updated two more times in month 32 (November 2026) and month 44 (November 2027). The revisions will ensure the programme to remain dynamic, user-centred, and aligned with emerging climate-related risks and research needs, ultimately promoting climate-informed decision-making and strengthening IRISCC's impact.

1 Introduction and scope of Version 2

Climate change–related risks (CCR) arise from the interaction between hazards, exposure, and vulnerability, affecting environmental systems, economic sectors, and societies across multiple domains. Addressing these risks requires integrated scientific approaches, coordinated research infrastructures (RIs), and effective translation of knowledge into adaptation and risk management strategies. IRISCC contributes to this objective by providing coordinated access to a broad portfolio of European RI services that support cross-domain climate risk research. By integrating the capabilities of multiple RIs across atmospheric, marine, terrestrial, and related domains, IRISCC aims to strengthen Europe’s capacity to generate robust, interoperable, and policy–relevant evidence for climate risk assessment and adaptation. The IRISCC Access Programme implements this objective through two complementary access modalities:

- Transnational Access (TA) to physical, remote, and hybrid services provided by the participating facilities/installations; and
- Virtual Access (VA) to digital services, tools, and data resources, initially based on existing RI services and progressively enhanced through project developments, including demonstrators and service design labs.

All services are visible, discoverable and accessible through the project’s [Catalogue of Services](#) (CoS), and are designed to enable cross-disciplinary collaboration, promote multi-RI engagement, foster integrated approaches to CCR assessment, and strengthen the evidence base for adaptation and climate risk management. The services are rolled out through three consecutive releases of the CoS, each with a defined level of integration and maturity: 1) the first service release, in month 12 (March 2025), is based on already existing single-RI services; 2) the second service release, scheduled for month 30 (September 2026), will offer integrated and customised RI services including tailored data products for multi-hazard risks (based on demonstrators developed during the project); 3) the third release, planned for month 40 (July 2027), will provide co-designed, transdisciplinary services developed and integrated through co-creation with user communities and societal stakeholders (via service design labs).

This document presents Version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme. It builds on the strategic basis defined in Version 1 which was published as project deliverable D7.2 ([Strategic IRISCC Access Programme – Version 1, in March 2025](#) (project month M12) [R1]). The update of the Access Programme aims at refining the overall approach and implementation of the calls. Version 2 reflects the transition from initial deployment to progressive improvement and consolidation. It does not change the programme’s core principles, including its flexible, open and bottom-up character. Rather, it introduces

selected refinements in access design, user support mechanisms and implementation practices, based on lessons learned from the first two TA-VA calls and opportunities since the first IRISCC CoS release in March 2025.

The document is structured as follows: Section 2 summarises observed trends and lessons learned from IRISCC TA-VA Calls 1 and 2, and presents the strategic adjustments and confirmed principles of the IRISCC access strategy. Section 3 provides the updated roadmap for upcoming access opportunities, with a particular focus on the design and implementation priorities for TA-VA Call 3. Section 4 presents the outlook and next steps, including priorities for subsequent calls and the progressive strengthening of TA-VA synergies. The Annex provides detailed access statistics for TA-VA Calls 1 and 2, information on fast-track access, and initial VA uptake indicators.

2 Strategic evolution of the IRISCC Access Programme

The transition of the IRISCC Access Programme from version 1 (see R1 in the Section 5 below) to version 2 reflects a focused refinement rather than a significant evolution. While the core objectives, i.e., promoting cross-disciplinary research to supporting climate risk assessments, remain unchanged, version 2 integrates adjustments based on lessons learned from the first IRISCC TA-VA Calls. These adjustments aim to strengthen the cross-domain engagement for addressing climate change related risks (CCR), without fundamentally changing the thematic priorities of the calls.

In parallel, the VA component has progressed through the onboarding, coordination and operational consolidation of the first release of the CoS, with services being accessible since April 2025. Efforts have primarily focused on service integration, user support, and the development of monitoring and feedback mechanisms to prepare for broader uptake.

2.1 Lessons learned since version 1

Annex 1 presents the statistics of the first two IRISCC TA-VA Calls and fast-track call, along with additional explanatory information. The first TA-VA Call was open from April to June 2025 and the second from September to November 2025, while the fast-track call as well as the VA opportunities remain continuously open. This section summarises the main lessons learnt from the responses to these calls and from the trends observed, as the basis for the strategic evolution of the IRISCC Access Programme in its current version 2.

2.1.1 User responses to initial TA-VA calls

The first two TA-VA calls provided valuable insights into user demographics, access preferences, and disciplinary trends:

User origin and geographical reach: TA Participation nearly doubled in Call 2, with 57 eligible proposals (vs. 26 in Call 1) and a much broader geographic reach, including 21% of users from outside Europe. While EU-based applicants remain dominant (70%), the increase in international participation likely reflects growing visibility of the programme and improved outreach and access facilitation measures, reflecting increasing global interest.

Target users and profiles: The access continues to primarily attract academic researchers (84%), with gradual increase in participation from SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises, 6%) and public authorities (9%). Gender representation is balanced, although project leadership

roles are predominantly held by men. Compared with Call 1, Call 2 shows greater involvement of expert scientists as project leaders, with continued participation of early-stage researchers as team members. This shift suggests growing confidence of senior scientific communities in the IRISCC access offer and an increasing interest of using IRISCC services in their research agendas.

Scientific domains: While the atmospheric domain remains dominant (52% in Call 1, 37% in Call 2), there is a strong interest in the ecological-biological (27%) and hydrological (24%) domain. Call 2 responses show a diversification of scientific fields with an increase in biomedical sciences as well as in new domains such as chemistry, information science, engineering and technology, and materials science. This indicates a gradual broadening of IRISCC's user base beyond traditional environmental sciences, toward more technical and applied research communities, reflecting the growing relevance of climate risk information across domains.

Requested facilities/installations and RIs: The number of facilities/installations requested increased markedly (from 15 in Call 1 to 25 in Call 2), indicating broader exploration of the IRISCC landscape. The demand is no longer concentrated primarily on atmospheric facilities (of ACTRIS ERIC), as there are increased requests toward EMBRC ERIC, eLTER, and EIRENE installations, which demonstrates a widening scope of environmental domains addressed.

Access preferences: Physical access (64%) remains the most requested access type, reflecting the importance of hands-on interaction with the RI facilities/installations and staff. Hybrid access (25%) remains of interest, while remote access (11%) remains limited, despite its potential to widen participation (and reduce logistical barriers and the environmental footprint).

Level of disciplinarity (interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary, and transdisciplinary): The share of interdisciplinary projects increased to 80% (from 54% in Call 1), while multidisciplinary projects decreased significantly (from 19% to 4%). However, closer analysis (as also reflected by the reviewers) indicates that level of integration is often superficial, with limited embedding in project design, methodology, and scientific rationale. Transdisciplinary projects remain rare (27% in Call 1, decreasing to 13% in Call 2), highlighting challenges in engaging non-academic stakeholders. Furthermore, reviewers also noted limitations in applicants' self-assessment of disciplinarity, potentially linked to the absence of a defined mono-disciplinary option.

Climate change risk (CCR) determinants: While single-determinant projects (e.g., hazard, exposure, or vulnerability) are common, considered by approximately half of the projects (54% in Call 1, 49% in Call 2), there is a notable increase in projects addressing multiple determinants (e.g., hazard-vulnerability: 15% in Call 1, 24% in Call 2). Although partially integrated approaches increased, the share of fully integrated projects (hazard-exposure-

vulnerability) remains limited (23% in Call 1, 16% in Call 2), suggesting a need for further guidance to better promote a more holistic CCR assessment approach.

These observations guide the strategic adjustments to the design of the calls and, consequently, this version 2 of the access programme, which places greater emphasis on deepening cross-disciplinary collaboration/integration and encouraging broader stakeholder involvement. They will also be taken into account in the upcoming communication and dissemination efforts (Deliverable D1.6 - Updated version of DEC strategy, month 24, March 2026), [R2] as well as in the organisation of the training activities (D3.1 [R3]). These observations are complemented by the KPIs developed in WP8 under task T8.4 to systematically monitor user profiles, access patterns, and service usage across TA and VA activities.

2.1.2 User responses to VA opportunities

Virtual Access (VA) for users to IRISCC services currently builds on the selection of (pre-) existing operational services of the participating RIs and has been available through IRISCC since the first release of the CoS in April 2025, as illustrated in Figure 1 To access VA services (<https://www.iriscc.eu/va>), users can identify them in the CoS but must register in the VA portal to accept the terms of use and gain access (no application required). VA is provided remotely, with support from the VA providers. The VA portfolio covers a broad range of climate-relevant digital services to support hazard characterisation, slow-onset climate processes, extreme event analysis, model evaluation, and climate impact studies across multiple CCR determinants. These include currently:

- (i) Climatologies and anomaly diagnostics of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and trace gases from airborne and ground-based observations (IAGOS, ACTRIS), supporting long-term trend analysis and extreme event detection;
- (ii) Near-real-time and quicklook services, including volcanic ash alerts, aerosol and cloud products, and identification of pollution or dust intrusion events;
- (iii) Tailored access to climate model data (**CMIP**, **CORDEX** [R4-R6]) and virtual research environments (VREs) for data processing, climate index computation, regriding, and impact-oriented analyses (IS-ENES);
- (iv) High-resolution observational datasets for soil moisture and snow depth across Europe (**ECA&D** [R6]), enabling drought and freshwater resource assessments; and
- (v) Greenhouse gas flux analysis and interactive tools for emissions trend analysis and anomaly detection (ICOS).

During the initial project period (April 2024–September 2026) VA efforts focused primarily on onboarding, technical integration, user support, and the establishment of monitoring mechanisms. Initial usage patterns (see Annex A2.1) indicate that the VA services are operational, internationally visible, and accessed by users across multiple world regions, with Europe remaining the dominant user base. A more detailed analysis of service uptake is provided in Deliverable D9.2 [R10]. Uptake varies across services, reflecting differences

which may be due to maturity of the RIs/services, access pathways, target communities, visibility and promotion efforts, alignment with the user requirements, as well as the type of functionality offered (e.g., data access, visualisation, or analytical environments) of the offered services. At this stage, available indicators of VA users capture access visits, downloads, requests from the IRISCC VA service providers, reflecting total service usage rather than IRISCC-specific attribution. This is because several IRISCC VA services are long-standing RI services that are also accessible directly through the specific RI portals. Information about downstream scientific outputs or detailed user profiles is not yet available, which is expected at this early stage of VA provision.

Greater emphasis has been placed on improving visibility and usability of the VA offer through IRISCC communication and dissemination channels. In particular, significant efforts have been made to enhance user navigation on the IRISCC website, ensuring that the service offering, covering TA, VA and the fast-track opportunities, is presented in a clearer and more accessible way. This includes explicitly communicating that VA services are continuously available and accessible at any time without the need for a specific application.

In parallel, IRISCC continues to consolidate harmonised usage monitoring and feedback tools, while further strengthening synergies between VA and TA to encourage more integrated use of physical, remote and virtual access modes. Elements of this integration were introduced in the design of the 3rd access call, where applicants were encouraged to develop proposals combining TA and VA services. In particular, the call highlighted VA integration as part of a broader set of key features, including cross-disciplinary approaches, integration across CCR determinants (hazard, exposure, vulnerability), and multi-RI collaboration (see [3rd Open Call for Access](#)). However, this aspect was only partially reflected in the supporting application and evaluation framework (e.g. form structure and evaluation criteria), limiting its full operationalisation, but is expected to be addressed in the design of the 4th access call, where a more structured integration of VA and TA dimensions should be explicitly considered within both the application template and evaluation framework. Over time, and as the project progresses, these efforts are expected to support a more robust assessment of user communities, disciplinary patterns, CCR coverage, and the extent to which different VA services are combined with TA, providing insights into the characteristics and maturity of services that best support integrated access pathways.

Looking ahead, communication efforts will increasingly focus on promoting individual services and their specific capabilities through targeted campaigns aimed at relevant user communities. In addition, a dedicated online hackathon will be organised, where users will rely primarily on VA services, particularly the more integrated solutions developed through the IRISCC demonstrators, to develop specific solutions/pilots. This initiative is expected to both enhance the visibility and uptake of VA services and provide direct feedback on user experience, tools, and service performance.

The second release of services in project month 30 (September 2026) will mark a strategic evolution of the IRISCC VA offer. It will introduce more integrated and customised scientific services, primarily targeting researchers, including tailored data products specifically focused on selected climate change risks topics and supporting multi-hazard risk assessments. The service developments build on six demonstrators (WP4) from the first half of the project [R9] and aim to strengthen and novel approaches of co-development of cross-RI services. The services will enable more complex TA and VA calls for scientific and technical integration, support interoperability among RIs (with WP6), including EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) and external catalogue alignment, thereby enhancing IRISCC's added value beyond the VA service aggregation.

2.2 Strategic adjustments and confirmed principles

Building on the lessons learnt as described in Section 2.1, version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme introduces targeted adjustments to improve the quality, integration, and impact of the user projects in the subsequent calls. These refinements, which are not meant to change the programme's core objectives, aim at strengthening cross-disciplinary collaboration¹, a more balanced use of RIs and their facilities, and more holistic climate risk assessment approaches. The TA-VA Call schedule introduced in version 1 will remain the same.

2.2.1 Adjustments to access design and implementation

The following eight measures are suggested to address the identified challenges and trends. Not all of these may be implemented in the next TA-VA calls, a stepwise approach with sufficient flexibility may therefore be considered.

1. Strengthening the assessment of cross-disciplinarity

Given that self-declared cross-disciplinarity often exceeds the actual level of integration observed, the evaluation process should be refined. Reviewers should explicitly assess the depth of disciplinary integration, using clear indicators (e.g., composition of user team and scientific profiles, co-design, integration of datasets and infrastructures, complementary methodologies, etc.) rather than relying on the applicants' self-classification only. The assessment should impact the overall score, with bonuses for mature and high-level cross-

¹ "Cross-disciplinary" is used here as an umbrella term covering multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary approaches, see also [R1] for more details.

disciplinary projects reserved for cases where these aspects are clearly embedded in the project (rather than compensating for other shortcomings in the project).

2. Encouraging multi-RI engagement

To foster stronger cross-domain integration, user projects will be encouraged (possibly required at some point) to address research spanning at least two RI domains or, alternatively, to request access to facilities/installations from at least two different domains. This will stimulate cross-RI collaboration, reduce thematic silos, and support more integrated CCR approaches. However, flexibility should remain for cases where a single-RI/single-facility setup is scientifically justified.

3. Extending time for co-design and user group composition

High-quality, cross-disciplinary projects require appropriate preparation time. Therefore, additional time could be allocated within the call timeline to allow the formation of the user group, the development of the project scope and methodological integration, and interaction with the service providers. This aims to shift projects from monodisciplinary and/or multidisciplinary approaches toward inter-/transdisciplinary co-design.

4. Promoting more integrated CCR approaches

To address the limited number of partially or fully integrated hazard-exposure-vulnerability projects, the call text and evaluation criteria should clarify the expectations by asking the applicants to better address an integrated approach of CCR components (avoid single determinants) in their objectives and justify the methodology. Reviewers should be asked to re-evaluate the level of integration, and additional bonus points could be awarded for proposals that i) integrate multiple determinants and/or ii) link with societal dimensions. However, this may require clear communication and provision of guidance notes to support the users.

5. Integrating Transnational Access (TA) with Virtual Access (VA) services

To enhance the scientific value and impact of the TA, stronger links between TA projects and the IRISCC VA services should be promoted. In particular, integrating the RIs' data services, tools, and digital resources could support improved interpretation and broader use of TA measurements and results during and beyond the physical/remote/hybrid access period. This could include comparison with existing datasets, models, and other RI integrated data products. This can be supported by encouraging TA users to integrate VA services into their project design, e.g., by complementing facility-based measurements and experiments with VA-supported data analysis or modelling services. Interaction between TA users and VA service providers should be facilitated during both project preparation and implementation. In addition, and where possible, datasets and results generated through TA should be made interoperable with the VA platforms (i.e., RI databases). To give incentives to such integration, dedicated consideration of TA-VA coherence within the evaluation framework will be further explored and developed for future access calls, including a potential introduction of specific recognition for proposals demonstrating a coherent TA-VA workflow. This approach supports more comprehensive and scalable climate risk analyses, improves data reusability, and strengthens the overall

coherence of the IRISCC service offer (see Section 2.1.2). More broadly, coordination across relevant project activities will benefit from structured exchange and synthesis mechanisms, including the TACT (TA Call Task Force), which brings together WP1, WP3, WP7, WP8 and WP11 as a strategic planning group to ensure that operational experience, user feedback, and analytical outputs are systematically considered in the strategic planning.

6. Strengthening underutilised RI installations

To better promote and facilitate access to currently underutilised RI installations, emphasis should be placed on increasing their visibility and clarifying their scientific added value within the access programme. This may include dedicated communication activities, clearer support to applicants, either by the project's access management team or the RIs/installations concerned, on the types of research questions and use cases their installations can support, and improved visibility of available capacities in the catalogue of services. Where appropriate, support mechanisms could help users identify suitable installations at an early stage of proposal development. Together, these elements would contribute to a more balanced use of the service portfolio and maximise the scientific return of the access programme. The practical modalities for implementation may require further consideration, including the potential use of targeted calls focused on underutilised installations.

7. Exploring thematic or problem-focused calls

Although the open thematic structure of the IRISCC access programme will be maintained, an additional targeted call addressing specific climate change risk challenges may be explored. These could either take the form of an additional call or replace one of the remaining TA-VA calls, depending on priorities and available resources. Examples of potential themes include compound hazards (i.e., hazards occurring simultaneously, such as heatwaves combined with ~~or~~ high pollution event) and sequential hazards (e.g., drought-induced soil drying followed by increased flood risks, with particular emphasis on societal impacts and integrated consideration of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability). Other thematic areas could focus on coastal vulnerability, extreme events on ecosystems, or similar high-impact situations. Such targeted calls could help attract new user communities, support more problem-oriented integration, and align infrastructure use with high-impact societal challenges.

8. Strengthening integration of the societal dimension in CCR research

To address the limited integration of vulnerability and societal factors in supported projects, future calls should place stronger emphasis on incorporating societal and economic dimensions into climate risk research. This may include involving expertise from societal sciences or policy-related domains (e.g., public authorities) to better link with the societal exposure and vulnerability. Given the challenges observed in achieving such integration in open calls, this approach may be more effectively implemented through targeted calls (see previous measure), where expectations regarding societal relevance and the consideration of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability can be more clearly framed. In this context, evaluation criteria could explicitly reflect these expectations and only very specific user projects may be selected, potentially supported by financial incentives in the form of

travel and subsistence support, to motivate the project teams. Clear guidance material and appropriate communication will nevertheless be essential to support applicants.

2.2.2 Financial support to IRISCC users

Adequate support for users' travel and subsistence (T&S) remains a critical factor for the attractiveness, inclusiveness and effective uptake of the IRISCC access programme. The extensive experience of the participating RIs in implementing access programmes demonstrates that an appropriate level of financial support to user groups can be decisive, particularly for enabling truly cross-disciplinary approaches, involving multiple RIs and user teams comprising multiple participants with complementary expertise in the user projects. The demand for T&S funds and support committed to date confirms its strategic importance. At the same time, the current level of user support foreseen may limit the feasibility of certain projects. **Within the constraints of the overall TA and VA access budgets, options to increase the allocation of financial support will be further explored, including the potential rebalancing between provider-based access costs and direct user support, to maximise user attractiveness, participation, and scientific impact.**

2.2.3 Communication actions

To support the adjustments introduced above, communication efforts will be reinforced to better guide applicants and broaden the diversity of the user community well in advance of and throughout each TA-VA call. Communication materials aim at clarifying the expectations regarding cross-disciplinary integration, the interaction of CCR determinants (hazard-exposure-vulnerability), the integration of societal dimensions in climate risk research and the constant availability of VA services. Particular emphasis will be placed on explaining complementarities between RIs and the added value of combining TA with VA services. In addition, guidance material presenting the evaluation criteria and associated scoring, ensuring transparency in the proposal selection process, is available both in the TA-VA User Handbook (<https://www.iriscc.eu/publication/transnational-virtual-access-handbook>) and on the IRISCC website. Observations presented in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 are being considered in the update of IRISCC dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) strategy published in March 2026 (D1.6, R2).

Beyond general communication improvements, IRISCC is progressively moving towards a more structured, service-oriented communication approach, where TA, VA, and Fast-Track access are communicated as clearly differentiated service lines, each supported by tailored messaging and user guidance. This includes reinforcing the role of VA as a continuously available service layer supporting both independent use and integration with TA-based experimental work.

Targeted outreach will aim to engage communities that have been less represented so far, including social sciences, policy-related domains, and non-academic stakeholders such as public authorities and SMEs. Communication actions may include updated call guidance documents, thematic webinars, information sessions, examples of good

practices from previously supported projects, and success stories. In addition, more interactive engagement formats—such as demonstrator-based showcases and co-creation activities including online hackathons—will be used to promote practical use of VA services and strengthen user feedback loops on tools, data products, and service performance.

Clear and early communication will also be essential to ensure that the call timelines effectively support proposal preparation, including, where appropriate, an extended call opening period as outlined in Section 2.2.1, and subject to its definition and communication. Experience shows that proposals are often submitted close to the deadline. **Early visibility of call content and expectations is therefore critical to allow applicants sufficient time to build consortia, engage with service providers, and support co-design between user teams and facilities from which the services are requested.** Together with the above actions, and in alignment with the revised communication campaign framework (Section 3.6, D1.6), these measures will strengthen the transition towards a more impact-driven dissemination strategy. This includes more targeted promotion of specific services, demonstrator-driven outreach, and the systematic use of success stories and user feedback to increase uptake and visibility of IRISCC services.

2.2.4 Training activities

Targeted training activities will support both users and service providers in implementing the strengthened integration objectives of the IRISCC access programme. To maximise the effectiveness of the training activities, they should be communicated sufficiently early and promoted throughout, allowing both users and providers adequate time to prepare, engage, and benefit from these activities.

For users, training will focus on project co-design across disciplines, improved integration of CCR determinants, effective use and combination of TA with VA services, and good practices in data management and interoperability, as well as proposal preparation and writing. This will help applicants design more coherent, methodologically integrated, and higher quality projects, and make better use of the IRISCC service ecosystem. To support this, training activities may include concrete example scenarios illustrating how different IRISCC services can be combined across RIs, including the use of VA services to complement on-site access. Such scenarios could serve as practical planning tools to help users better design integrated projects.

From the providers' perspective, engagement is primarily focused on ensuring the feasibility of user proposals and their capacity to deliver the requested access. Within this framework, training and capacity-building activities should therefore be understood as RI-level support measures, building on existing practices rather than introducing new mandatory responsibilities for individual installations. These activities aim to facilitate cross-RI collaboration and co-design with user teams, and to promote cross-RI collaboration and co-design with user teams, and to promote best practices for

data management and interoperability of outputs generated through TA activities with IRISCC and RI VA platforms, where and when relevant, to maximise visibility, accessibility, and impact. Exchange of experience between RIs will be encouraged to harmonise practices and improve user support. Together, these activities will strengthen the quality of supported projects and the overall coherence of IRISCC service delivery.

IRISCC training activities are described in public Deliverable D3.1 IRISCC training and knowledge exchange plan [R3], published in month 10 (January 2025) and will be reported in upcoming Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3, Reports from training activities Part I and Part II in autumn 2026 and summer 2028, respectively. Roadmap on ensuring sustainability of training activities, including revision of training needs and uptake feedback and experience gained will be reported in Deliverable D3.5 at the end of the project (September 2028).

3 Updated roadmap to IRISCC access opportunities and expected impact

3.1 Updated access schedule and planning of calls

The IRISCC access roadmap reconfirms the maintenance of the call schedule as presented in version 1 of the Access Programme (Figure 1), while now also displaying the continuous VA opportunities. In line with this schedule, **a TA-VA call (Call 3) was launched in February 2026, with a two-month opening period.** The opening periods of the subsequent calls may be slightly adjusted (extended), where appropriate, to accommodate the measures proposed in Section 2.2.1, in particular to allow additional time for project preparation and co-design by the user teams. This progressive approach aims at improving the scientific integration, access uptake, and impact.

Figure 1. Overall IRISCC access call schedule showing the timing of the transnational (TA), virtual (VA), and fast-track access opportunities, as well as of the three releases of the catalogue of services (CoS).

3.2 Type and theme for TA-VA calls 3 and 4

TA-VA call 3 will remain an open, bottom-up call, open to all user communities provided that proposals clearly address climate change-related risks in line with the IRISCC thematic framework, while placing stronger emphasis on scientific integration and effective use of the IRISCC access offers. Building on the analysis of previous calls and discussions within the consortium, several targeted measures (Section 2.2.1) will be implemented in Call 3, with the objectives of clarifying expectations for applicants through targeted communication and training actions and strengthening the evaluation framework:

- (1) **In Call 3, the assessment of disciplinaryity will be refined.** Applicants will be explicitly invited to indicate whether their project follows a mono-disciplinary or cross-disciplinary approach. While mono-disciplinary projects remain eligible, it will be clearly communicated that well-justified cross-disciplinary approaches are expected to score higher when they are coherent with the overall project design.

Reviewers will be asked to assess the level of disciplinary using clearer indicators, such as the composition and complementarity of the user team, scientific profiles, co-design elements, methodological integration, and the coherence of the workplan and scientific rationale.

- (2) **Call 3 will strengthen the multi-RI engagement.** While this aspect is already included as an evaluation criterion, Call 3 will be accompanied by targeted communication and training actions to facilitate access to services across RIs, including both the user of multiple RIs and the use of multiple installations within and across RIs. In the case of co-located installations contributing to more than one RI, the call documentation and user interface should clearly indicate the RI(s) responsible for each service, ensuring transparency for both applicants and evaluators. These efforts aim to prepare the ground for future calls where multi-RI access may be further encouraged or incentivised.
- (3) **Call 3 will promote a more integrated Climate Change Risk (CCR) approach,** encouraging applicants to better consider and combine the key CCR determinants –hazard, exposure, and vulnerability– within their project design. Integrated approaches will be positively reflected in the scoring, provided they are scientifically justified and aligned with project objectives and methods. Reviewers will be guided to assess how effectively the selected determinants are addressed and integrated, based on indicators such as coherence with objectives, methodological robustness, and expected impact.
- (4) **Call 3 will aim at encouraging stronger integration of VA services within TA projects.** Applicants will be invited to consider combining experimental or observational access with VA-supported services, such as data analysis tools, modelling, or other digital services. This aspect is planned to be further strengthened in subsequent access calls, including a more explicit and structured consideration of VA integration within the evaluation process. To support this objective, the effective integration of VA services could be considered as an added value in the overall scoring framework.

Additional measures –such as extending the open-call timeline, launching targeted topical calls, focusing on under-utilised facilities, or strengthening links to the social domain (see section 2.1.1)– will not be implemented in Call 3 but will be further explored in the context of subsequent calls.

Call 4, to be launched in July 2026, will follow the same structural and thematic framework as Call 3, ensuring continuity of the updated access design while allowing for targeted fine-tuning of communication and implementation based on emerging feedback and uptake patterns. The process is supported by the TA Call Task Force (TACT), which provides a structured feedback loop between implementation experience, user input, and strategic planning.

Finally, all measures introduced in Call 3 and Call 4 will be supported by appropriate communication actions, guidance documents, and training activities, targeting both user communities and service providers. These supporting elements will be developed within the relevant work packages (WPI, 3, 9-10) and consistently embedded into access-related materials, including application forms and evaluation templates (WP8), to ensure clarity, transparency, and coherence across the Access Programme.

3.3 Expected implementation and impact

Expected implementation

The implementation of version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme is expected to progressively enhance the scientific quality, integration, and impact of supported projects in the framework of IRISCC, while improving the coherence and visibility of the overall IRISCC service offer.

The targeted measures proposed for Call 3 and 4 will be implemented by IRISCC with a particular emphasis on:

- a clearer evaluation framework for cross-disciplinary integration and CCR determinant coverage;
- strengthened criteria and incentives for multi-RI engagement;
- enhanced communication and training activities to support co-design during proposal preparations;
- reinforced communication on the availability and relevance of VA services for TA projects.

These measures are expected to result in improved proposal quality already in Call 3, including stronger integration of VA services in TA project design, greater cross-RI collaboration, and more robust cross-disciplinary approaches.

In parallel, optimising user financial support (T&S) is expected to further strengthen use uptake, particularly for cross-RI and cross-disciplinary collaborations. Adequate support for users remains an important factor for encouraging broad participation and ambitious project design, allowing equal opportunities for users regardless of their geographical location or home institutions' support.

Based on the positive trend observed between Calls 1 and 2, further growth in proposal numbers and geographic diversity is sought. Continued outreach and improved guidance are expected to attract a broader range of scientific domains, including technical and applied research communities, increase participation of non-academic stakeholders, such as SMEs and public authorities, and promote deeper cross-disciplinary collaboration and more balanced use of RI facilities. Over time, improved monitoring mechanisms, supported

by the KPIs developed in WP8 for systematic monitoring of user profiles and access patterns, will enable more precise analysis of user communities, including career stages, sectoral distribution, gender balance, and international participation. The access programme will be updated when needed to better guarantee and support equal opportunities.

Expected scientific impact

A stronger focus on integrated hazard–exposure–vulnerability approaches is expected to improve the robustness and relevance of the supported research projects. By encouraging multi-RI engagement, improved co-design, and integration of TA and VA opportunities, the programme aims to:

- Enable more comprehensive, cross-domain climate risk assessments;
- Foster methodological innovation through combined use of observational, experimental, and modelling resources;
- Enhance the visibility and uptake of scientific outputs, including datasets and publications, and improve the reusability across RIs.

The development of the second release of the CoS, with particular focus on integrated, cross-RI-developed demonstrators targeting multi-hazard risk areas, is expected to further enhance the scientific added value of IRISCC.

Expected societal impact

Through stronger integration of vulnerability and societal dimensions, as well as targeted outreach to policy-related communities, the IRISCC access programme seeks to increase the relevance of supported projects for adaptation planning and climate risk management. Over time, this may contribute to:

- Improved data and knowledge for climate risk assessment and adaptation strategies;
- Better linkage between environmental observations, modelling, and societal impact analysis;
- Enhanced support to public authorities and decision-makers.

While societal impact is expected to develop progressively and often beyond the immediate duration of access projects, Version 2 aims to better facilitate these outcomes. In particular, a further strengthening is foreseen with the third CoS release, when co-designed knowledge services produced in Service Design Labs are integrated into the VA service portfolio, thereby enhancing their relevance for policy makers and other societal users.

4 Outlook and next steps

Version 2 of the IRISCC Access Programme confirms the overall strategic direction established in version 1, while introducing targeted refinements to enhance integration, coherence, and impact. The analysis of the first two TA-VA calls demonstrates strong and growing interest from the scientific community, increasing international engagement, and diversification of user domains. These trends are possibly driven by increased visibility of the programme, progressive improvements in access implementation, and the first effects of targeted outreach and TA-VA integration measures. At the same time, it highlights the need to deepen cross-disciplinary integration, strengthen multi-RI collaboration, and better embed the hazard-exposure-vulnerability approach in project design.

Call 3 represents an important transitional step. It implements key refinements (e.g., regarding disciplinary assessment, CCR integration, multi-RI engagement, TA-VA integration) while maintaining the open, bottom-up character of the programme.

Call 4, launched in July 2026, will build on this transitional phase and will serve as an operational feedback-driven iteration, allowing adjustments to communication and implementation based on the outcomes of Call 3. This iterative process is supported by TACT, ensuring systematic integration of operational experience and user feedback into strategic adjustments. The experience from Call 3 will support the preparation of Call 4 and subsequent calls.

Looking ahead, the following priorities will be considered in the next versions of the access programme (v3 and v4):

- Results from monitoring TA and VA and related user feedback;
- Strengthened support for early-stage co-design of projects to promote cross-disciplinary integration and effective use of multiple RIs already starting in the proposal preparation phase;
- Further strengthening of TA-VA synergies across RIs, with a focus on improving usability and relevance of services for a broader range of user profiles;
- Enhanced visibility and balanced use of underutilised RIs and installations, including through targeted communication and outreach actions;
- Optimisation of user financial support (T&S), where additional dedicated resources re defined and agreed through project governance (Executive Board/General Assembly), to improve feasibility and access uptake in support of CCR objectives;
- Exploration of targeted or problem-focused calls addressing specific multi-hazard or high-impact climate risk themes;

- Increased integration of societal dimensions within CCR research;
- Continued support through communication and training activities to foster high-quality proposals.

The second release of the CoS in September 2026, followed by Call 5 in December 2026, will introduce more integrated and customised scientific services, building on the six VA demonstrators developed during the first half of the project. This evolution is expected to enhance IRISCC's added value by moving from access to existing services toward more coherent, interoperable, and impact-oriented service provision.

Overall, the IRISCC Access Programme remains on track and is consolidating its initial approach. The refinements introduced in version 2 aim not to change its core objectives, but to progressively increase the level of integration, strengthen user support mechanisms, broaden the diversity of user communities, and enhance the scientific and societal impact of supported activities in the remaining project period.

The version 3 of the IRISCC Access Programme is expected to be published in November 2026 (M32), taking into account the statistics of Call 3 and first feedback from the launch of Call 4 in July 2026, as well as of the second release of the COS. The final version 4 is planned for November 2027 (M44), after the end of the last access call (to be launched in May 2027).

5 References

References	
No	Description/Link
R1	IRISCC Deliverable D7.2, V01 – Strategic IRISCC Access Programme, Version 1. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102250
R2	IRISCC Deliverable D1.6 – Updated version of DEC strategy. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19217917
R3	IRISCC Deliverable D3.1 – IRISCC training and knowledge exchange plan. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14777158
R4	CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project) website, visited in 2026: https://wcrp-cmip.org/
R5	CORDEX (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) website, visited in 2026: https://cordex.org/
R6	ECA&C (European Climate Assessment & Dataset) website, visited in 2026: https://www.ecad.eu/
R7	IRISCC Deliverable D8.2 – Optimised IRISCC VA Management System. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15592864
R8	IRISCC Deliverable D9.1 – Report defining and describing (virtual) R1 services. https://zenodo.org/records/15774382
R9	IRISCC Deliverable D4.1 – Report on the full Demonstrator design https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880714
R10	IRISCC Deliverable D9.2 – First report with statistics on use of the R1 services including assessment reports from https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20509730

Annex 1 – Call statistics

This Annex provides an overview of the access statistics and patterns observed in the first two IRISCC TA-VA calls. The information presented here complements the strategic analysis discussed in Sections 2 and 3, and serves as a basis for illustrating the evolution of user demand and target users, disciplinary coverage, and other access-related aspects. Statistics and graphical representations are provided for each call to support the assessment of trends and emerging patterns. A more detailed overview of access statistics and metrics related to the first two calls (TA only) is available in Milestone 33 - 1st intermediate report of the access provision, submitted in March 2026 (project’s internal report).

A1.1 TA-VA Call 1 statistics (TA only)

The first IRISCC TA-VA call attracted 27 submitted TA proposals, of which 26 were eligible and selected for access. One proposal was ineligible as not considered transnational. Below presented is a selected list of user and access statistics for these 26 supported TA user projects.

A1.1.1 User origin, target users, scientific field, profile, gender (C1)

The call received applications from 14 countries, including two non-EU countries (Turkey, United Kingdom), which accounted for 7% of the requests, as well as three international user groups from outside Europe (China, United States), representing 11% of the requests, as illustrated in Figure A1.1. A total of 71 users requested access in Call 1 projects, including 11 single-user applications and 15 user groups. A more detailed geographical representation of the users’ affiliations is given in Figure A1.2. The graphs demonstrate an early international reach of the IRISCC access offer, beyond the immediate European research area.

Figure A1.1. Origin of TA user group leaders’ hosting institutions in first IRISCC call.

Figure A1.2: Origin of users hosting institutions, including the user group leader and all group members. Source: Graph provided by Rosa Petracca Altieri (CNR), as presented within the IRISCC consortium.

The user community was predominantly academic in nature (respectively 87% of 90.1%, depending on the categorisation into stakeholder groups or institution status), complemented by a limited number of societal and commercial users, see Figure A1.3. Although the profiles reflect a strong initial uptake by the academic research community, a small emerging interest from non-academic sectors can be noted.

Figure A1.3. TA target users in first IRISCC call. The upper graph should the user stakeholder groups as defined within the project. The bottom graph (source: as Figure A.1.2) indicates the user institution status.

The majority of users are male users (54%), despite a strong participation of female users, see Figure A1.4. Relatively fewer women are group leaders (40%) compared to men (60%).

Figure A1.4. Gender of users (source: as Figure A.1.2).

The user profile shows a strong participation of academic researchers across all career stages (Figure A1.5), with First Stage (R1) and Leading Researchers (R4) most prominently represented, both as project leaders and team members. In terms of scientific domains, applications are clearly dominated by Atmospheric sciences (ENV-ATMO, 52%), followed by Eco-biosphere (ENV-ECOBIO, 31%) and Hydrosphere (ENV-HYDRO, 13%), while Bio-medical and Lithosphere domains remain marginal (2% and 1%, respectively).

Figure A1.5. User profile and their scientific fields (source: as Figure A.1.2).

A1.1.2 Requested facilities and access types (C1)

Call 1 projects requested access to 15 different facilities and installations, from more than 70 physical facilities/installations participating in IRISCC (Figure A1.6), with 9 facilities/installations having received more than one application.

Figure A1.6. TA Facilities/installations requested in the first Call (left, source: Klaus Steenberg Larsen, UCPH as presented to the IRISCC consortium) and associated RIs (right).

Physical access (PA) has been the predominant access type (69%, see Figure A1.7), reflecting that users see hands-on access at the facilities/installations as central to achieving their scientific objectives. Purely remote access (RA) is less frequently requested (8%), while hybrid access (HA, combining physical and remote access) remains of interest (23%).

Figure A1.7. TA Access types requested during the first call, including physical (PA), remote (RA), and hybrid (HA) access.

A1.1.3 Climate change risk determinants and disciplinarity (C1)

Climate change risks are commonly understood as the result of the interaction between hazards, exposure, and vulnerability, reflecting both the characteristics of climate-related events and the susceptibility and resilience of the affected systems (Figure A1.8).

Figure A1.8. Key determinants of the climate change related risks in IRISCC (hazard, exposure, vulnerability).

The analysis of the first Call shows that almost half of the user projects focus on a single determinant only which, on its own, provides limited context for a climate change risk (CCR) assessment. Projects addressing overlapping determinants remain more limited (hazard–vulnerability: 15%; hazard–exposure: 8%), see Figure A1.9. Only 23% of projects adopt a more integrated hazard–exposure–vulnerability approach, reflecting a growing recognition of the need for holistic frameworks to capture the complexity of climate change risks.

Figure A1.9. Distribution of TA user projects of Call 1, according to the climate change risk (CCR) determinants considered, including hazard, exposure, vulnerability, and their combinations.

The majority of supported projects are interdisciplinary (54%), highlighting the need to integrate multiple perspectives when addressing climate change risks (Figure A1.10). Transdisciplinary projects represent 27%, while multidisciplinary approaches account for a more limited share (19%).

However, it needs to be considered that the level of interdisciplinary results from the users' self-assessment. Reviewer feedback shows that the depth of integration varies considerably, and that interdisciplinarity is sometimes asserted rather than fully embedded in the project design and work plan. Truly transdisciplinary approaches remain relatively rare.

Figure A1.10. Level of disciplinary of TA user projects in Call 1, distinguishing interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and multidisciplinary research.

A1.2 TA-VA Call 2 statistics (TA only)

The second IRISCC call attracted 59 submitted TA proposals, of which 57 are considered eligible. The selection of proposals for access is currently ongoing. An overview of key user and access statistics for these 57 supported projects is provided below.

A1.2.1 User origin, target users, scientific field, profile, gender (C2)

The call received applications from a total of 24 countries, including 14 EU countries, 2 non-EU countries (Turkey, United Kingdom), and 8 international countries outside Europe (Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, Chile, Jordan, US). Of the 57 eligible projects, 40 (70%) are from EU countries, 5 (9%) from non-EU countries, and 12 (21%) from international countries, as illustrated in Figure A1.11. A total of 141 eligible TA users requested access in Call 2 projects, including 11 single-user applications and 15 user groups. Figure A.2 provides a detailed geographical representation of the users' affiliations. These data show a wide engagement both within Europe and internationally, with a notable share of users from countries outside the EU. Call 2 attracted a substantially higher number of TA users (141 compared with 71) and a larger number of eligible applications (57 compared with 26), while maintaining a similar geographical diversity. Although EU countries still account for the majority of requests, the presence of non-EU and in particular international users confirms a strengthening trend toward broader international participation in IRISCC access activities.

Figure A1.11. Origin of TA user group leaders' hosting institutions in the 2nd IRISCC call (left) and map of affiliation countries (right, source: as Figure A.1.2).

The user community was largely composed of academic institutions, with universities and higher education accounting for 56% of participants and public research organizations contributing an additional 28%. Public authorities represented 9% of users, while small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) made up 6%, and other users 1%, as illustrated in Figure A1.12. These figures show that Call 2 primarily attracted the academic research community, while also reflecting a small but emerging interest from non-academic sectors. Compared with Call 1, Call 2 shows a slight increase in participation from public authorities and SMEs,

suggesting a growing engagement of non-academic stakeholders alongside the established academic user base.

Figure A1.12. TA Target users in IRISCC Call 2.

Similar to Call 1, in Call 2 the majority of TA users are male users (53%), but there remains a strong participation of female users, see Figure A1.13. Out of the 141 projects, 46 principal investigators (PIs) are male (with 29 additional male users) and 40 are female PIs (with 25 additional female users), highlighting a relatively balanced gender representation within the user community, including both project leaders and participants.

Figure A1.13. Gender of users (left), and role in the user group (right). Source: as figure A.1.2.

In Call 1, the user community was strongly composed of academic researchers at all career stages. Call 2 shows a significant expansion in both participation and diversity of roles (Figure A1.14). Leading Researchers (R4) and Established Researchers (R3) are now more numerous as project leaders, while First Stage Researchers (R1) continue to represent a large fraction of team members. The distribution across scientific domains has shifted slightly: Atmospheric sciences (ENV-ATMO) remain the largest domain (52 projects, 37%),

followed by Eco-biosphere (38 projects, 27%) and Hydrosphere (33 projects, 24%). Bio-medical sciences (BIO-MED) have increased slightly (7 projects, 5%). New domains such as Chemistry (CHEM, 4%) and Information Science (ISC), Material Sciences (MS), Engineering and Technology (ENG-TECH), each with 1 project (~1%), appear, reflecting a broadening of research areas covered by the TA-VA calls. Call 2 seems to have attracted a larger and more diverse user community, both in terms of career stage and research fields, while maintaining strong engagement from the established academic core. There is also a clear trend toward expanding participation beyond traditional environmental sciences, suggesting a growing interdisciplinarity in IRISCC access.

Figure A1.14. TA User profiles and their scientific fields in Call 2 (source: as figure A.1.2).

A1.2.2 Requested facilities and access types (C2)

For Call 2, projects requested access to 25 different IRISCC facilities / installations, reflecting an increase in both the number of facilities targeted and the overall demand compared to Call 1 (Figure A1.15). Compared to Call 1, where projects requested access to 15 different facilities and installations, Call 2 demonstrates a clear expansion in interest. ACTRIS ERIC (30%) and EMBRC ERIC (26%) continue to attract the highest number of requests, while eLTER (19%) and EIRENE (12%) show a notable increase in demand compared to Call 1. In contrast, AnaEE (7%) sees fewer requests this time, though 5% are targeting joint ANAEE/eLTER installation. Overall, the trend indicates a broader diversification in facility usage, reflecting varying levels of demand.

Figure A1.15. TA Facilities/installations requested in Call 2.

The types of access observed in Call 2 are very similar to Call 1. Physical access (PA) continues to dominate, accounting for 64% of requests (see Figure A1.16), reflecting the importance users place on on-site, hands-on access interactions at the facilities/installations to meet their scientific objectives. Requests for remote access (RA) remain limited (11%), while hybrid access (HA), combining physical and remote access, continues to attract a substantial interest (25%).

Figure A1.16. TA Access types requested during Call 2, including physical (PA), remote (RA), and hybrid (HA) access.

A1.2.3 Climate change risk determinants and disciplinaryity (C2)

The analysis of the climate change risks (CCR) determinants addressed in Call 2 indicates that nearly half of the user projects (49%) continue to address a single determinant only:

most often hazards (27%), or vulnerability (18%), and some few exposure (4%), see Figure A1.17. Projects combining multiple determinants are more prominent than in Call 1, particularly those addressing hazard–vulnerability interactions (24%, compared to 15% in Call 1) and, to a lesser extent, exposure–vulnerability (9%, not addressed in Call 1), and few hazard–exposure (2%, compared to 8% in Call 1). Despite this increase in partially integrated approaches, only 16% of projects simultaneously address hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Compared with Call 1 (23%), this represents a slight decline in a fully integrated approach, suggesting that while awareness of multi-determinant perspectives is growing, holistic project designs remain to be better developed.

Figure A1.17. Distribution of TA user projects of Call 2, according to the climate change risk (CCR) determinants considered, including hazard, exposure, vulnerability, and their combinations.

Concerning the level of disciplinarity of the TA user project in Call 2, the results indicate that multidisciplinary approaches have declined to 7% (compared to Call 1 with 19%), see Figure A1.18. However, there is a shift toward interdisciplinary projects, which account for 80% (compared to 54% in Call 1). The number of transdisciplinary projects (13%) is slightly higher than in Call 1 but is still not significant, due to challenges in engaging non-academic user or achieving cross-domain collaboration. As mentioned for Call 1, these results are based on self-reported assessments, whose accuracy remains questionable.

Figure A1.18. Level of disciplinarity of TA user projects in Call 2, distinguishing interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and multidisciplinary research.

A1.3 Fast-track access statistics

As described in Version 1 of the Access Programme (see reference R1), IRISCC provides a fast-track access pathway to accelerate access in justified priority situations. This mechanism applies in cases of (i) unexpected or urgent events requiring an immediate scientific response (e.g. extreme weather events or sudden environmental crises), and (ii) to support the participation of researchers affiliated with Ukrainian organisations, in recognition of the exceptional circumstances affecting the Ukrainian scientific community.

In 2025, IRISCC has received two fast-track TA proposals. The proposals underwent immediate evaluation in line with the fast-track procedure (see details in table A1.1). One of the proposals received a positive evaluation and was accepted for access. The second proposal is still under review, as the initially requested service provider was unable to accommodate the request. The possibility of access via an alternative installation is currently being explored.

More detailed quantitative information on the fast-track access will be provided in a future version of this document, once additional data become available.

Table A1.1. Statistics related to fast-track access requests

Fast-track access proposals	#1	#2
User characteristics		
Origin (affiliated institution)	Ukraine	Ukraine
User group	Public research	University and higher education
Scientific field	ENV-ATMO	ENV-HYDRO
User profile	Leading researcher (PI), 1 established (R3) and 2 first stage researchers (R4)	R3 – Established Researcher
Requested facilities and access types		
Requested RI/facilities	ACTRIS (SMEAR II)	EMBRC (Umeå Marine Sciences Centre)
Access type	Hybrid (PA by R4)	Hybrid
CRR determinants and disciplinarity		
CRR determinants	Hazards + Exposure	Hazards + Exposure + Vulnerability
Disciplinarity	Interdisciplinary	Transdisciplinary

A2.1 VA statistics

IRISCC Virtual Access (VA), as part of the TA-VA calls, provides free and unrestricted online access to services and resources related to CCR. A centralized and harmonized system for managing virtual user access has been implemented, with VA being managed centrally to ensure a uniform, standard service provision as well as a unique interface for users through the [VA portal](#) and link with Catalogue of services (CoS), where all VA services are listed and fully described. The VA services are accessed through the data centres of the respective RIs participating in IRISCC. More information on VA services and management is available in Deliverables D8.2 [R8], D9.1 [R9] and D9.2 [R10] see Section 5.

IRISCC's VA has been continuously open since April 2025, with particular promotion done through the various TA-VA calls. It is currently provided to existing services after the first CoS release. The usage statistics presented below reflect the situation at the end of the first reporting period (RPI), covering approximately six months of service availability within the project. The metrics are not yet fully harmonised across providers, and the numbers presented in Table A2.1 should be interpreted as indicative of uptake rather than strictly comparable indicators. It should also be noted that users may access these operational and existing services either through via the IRISCC CoS or directly through the respective RI's data portals. In the latter case, it remains challenging to determine how many of these users can be attributed specifically to IRISCC, which may lead to an over- or underestimation of IRISCC-specific uptake.

Current indicators measure various access events including visits, downloads, or other requests. Harmonised usage tracking and user feedback tools are under development to enable more robust cross-service comparison in future reporting periods. Overall, Europe remains the dominant regions of users, but there is notable uptake from Asia, North America, and other world regions.

Table A2.1. Quantity of users and geographical origin per VA service in RPI.

VA installation name	Quantity of users	Geographical user origin
IAGOS DC	164 users	90% Europe, 8% Middle East, 2% USA
ACTRIS DC (NILU)	1812 visits to visualisation webpage, 87 eBC data downloads	Visits: 85% Europe, 7% Asia, 6.7% North America, Downloads: 68% Europe, 17% North America, 14% Asia
ACTRIS DC (CNR)	- Quicklook service (statistics available since 7/2025): 528 visits and 1513 pages - Level 3 climatological products: 580 DOI resolutions	Quicklook service visits: 73.5% Europe, 14.4% North America, 7.6% Asia, 3.8% South America, 0.6% Africa, 0.2% Oceania

VA installation name	Quantity of users	Geographical user origin
ICOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 14,200 unique users per year, ~2 million downloads - Jupyter: 200 unique users - Curve 100 visitors per day since release (2 weeks) 	80% Europe: 8% China, 6% North America, 4% South America, 1% Asia (other), <1% Africa
IS-ENES (DKRZ)	>20000 requests per day, estimated 200 users (assuming 10 requests per user, back-tracking to individual users is currently not possible). Total > 1000 users during IRISCC	Only European users counted in quantity of users. Non-EU users will be considered in future statistics
IS-ENES (KNMI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visits: >1072 - Build downloads (metalink): >438 users - Bulk DataStaging to workspace: >59 users. Numbers are assumed to be underestimated as ad-blocker users are not tracked. Total registered accounts: 242 	45% Europe, 24% Asia, 11.7% Africa, 9.7% North America, 7.2% South America, 2.4% Oceania